

DIFFUSIVE STRESS RELAXATION DURING CREEP OF ALIGNED WHISKER-REINFORCED Mg-Li ALLOY

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ABSTRACT

Compressive creep tests have been carried out with whisker-reinforced composites based on 20 vol.% SiC in a Mg-11 wt.% Li matrix, a single phase bcc alloy exhibiting very high creep rates at low homologous temperatures. Over the temperature range 25°C-170°C (0.3-0.5 T_m), the composite creep data are consistent with a stress exponent of about 8-9 and an activation energy of about 80-90 kJ mole⁻¹. At somewhat higher temperatures, it would appear that a transition takes place towards behaviour with an activation energy of about 130-140 kJ mole⁻¹. The volume diffusion activation energy for Li in this alloy is about 135-140 kJ mole⁻¹, so that these results may be consistent with dislocation climb being the rate-determining mechanism, controlled by core or interfacial diffusion at $T \sim 0.3-0.5 T_m$ and by volume diffusion at $T \geq 0.6 T_m$. Material has been produced with two different mean whisker lengths and data from these indicate a definite increase in creep resistance with length, although the exponent describing the dependence appears from these very limited data to have a magnitude of less than unity. Anomalously high activation energy and stress exponent values, reported for other systems, have not been detected. This may be a consequence of the lower internal stresses and temperatures involved in this study, compared with previous experimental work on aluminium-based composites.

INTRODUCTION

There is current interest in the creep behaviour of particle- and whisker-reinforced metal matrix composites. A number of experimental studies have examined creep by means of both tension and torsion tests, over a range of temperature and strain rates.⁽¹⁻⁵⁾ Attention has also been focused recently on the effect of thermal cycling under load, which tends to enhance the creep rate.⁽⁶⁻⁸⁾ The vast majority of these tests have been carried out on aluminium-based composites, containing SiC particles or SiC whiskers. The latter have in most cases been aligned along the stress axis by an extrusion process, although this operation has frequently reduced the aspect ratio to a relatively small value (≤ 8). A complication arises during torsion testing in that the direction of fibre alignment tends to change with respect to the principal stress axes during the test. It is expected that the steady-state creep rates should conform to a simple generic equation of the form

$$\dot{\epsilon} = A \delta^p \sigma_0^n \exp(-Q/RT) \quad (1)$$

where the stress exponent n should be low (~ 1) in a regime dominated by vacancy transport, but higher ($\sim 3-8$) when (diffusion-assisted) dislocation motion controls matrix deformation. The activation energy Q should be that for the rate-determining diffusional process, but the significance of a diffusion length δ (related to reinforcement dimensions) and the expected value of the exponent p remain unclear. It seems probable that the grain size will be relevant here if it is not larger than the spacing between the inclusions. Among the various assumptions incorporated into the model is that there is embedded in the parameter A some proportionality constant between local and macroscopic strain rate values: the magnitude of this is expected to change with the volume fraction of reinforcement.

Several authors^(1,2,4) have observed various anomalies, such as the absence of a threshold stress, very high stress exponents and activation energies that appeared variable with strain rate but were, in general, very high (much greater than that for volume diffusion in the matrix). Although some of these effects may have been partly due to microstructural factors (such as severe inhomogeneities of ceramic distribution), uncertainties clearly exist concerning the nature of deformation mechanisms. An idea increasingly proposed is that internal stresses from differential thermal contraction play a dominant role. These stresses will vary with temperature and because they may play an important part in determining local relaxation kinetics, an apparently anomalous variation of flow stress with temperature is recorded. It has been proposed^(4,9) that the apparent activation energy should be related to the true value by

$$Q_a = Q - (d\sigma_I/dT)(nRT/(\sigma - \sigma_I)) \quad (2)$$

where σ_I is the internal stress.

In the present work, steady-state compressive creep is examined with a matrix which exhibits pronounced creep at a relatively low homologous temperature. Magnesium alloyed with more than about 11 wt.% Li is single phase bcc, with a congruent freezing temperature of almost 600°C, but has a flow stress at room temperature of only about 50-70 MPa and exhibits very high ductility⁽¹⁰⁾. This behaviour is believed to be associated with fast diffusion kinetics exhibited by the lithium in this phase^(11,12). Although a Mg-Li/SiC composite has a very large thermal expansion mismatch, internal stresses are likely to be limited by rapid relaxation. In addition, creep behaviour can be explored at relatively low absolute temperatures, which should reduce the discrepancy between apparent and true activation energies predicted by equation (2). It has been found⁽¹³⁾ that SiC whiskers remain chemically stable in Mg-Li alloys over a wide range of temperature.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The composites were produced by squeeze infiltration⁽¹⁴⁾ of whisker preforms containing a few wt.% of silica-based binder. This was followed by machining of a cylindrical billet with the axis lying in the plane of whisker alignment, which was extruded to give a bar of about 10 mm diameter. Both infiltration and extrusion have been carried out in a vacuum chamber under an argon atmosphere, although it is possible for the extrusion to be done in air (providing the oxidized surface layers are subsequently removed). Details of the processing conditions are given elsewhere⁽¹³⁾. The whisker volume fraction was about 20% in all cases. The extrusion was carried out at different temperatures and strain rates, so as to give different degrees of fibre fracture during the process⁽¹⁵⁾. TEM examination is hampered by a tendency towards lithium loss during thinning, or severe oxidation of the foil, but, in general, observations have suggested that the grain size is of the same order as the whisker spacing. In the present work, two types of material have been tested, corresponding to extrusion conditions giving rise to different average whisker aspect ratios. These aspect ratios were estimated by an extraction technique in which the matrix was dissolved in sulphuric acid. The resulting suspension was diluted and then allowed to sediment onto a metal plate, which was examined with the SEM. About 150 whiskers were examined for each material. In this way, it was possible to separate most of the whiskers and use image analysis to evaluate length and aspect ratio averages. Both number- and volume-averaged mean values were obtained for these two parameters, using the formulae

$$L = \left(\sum_{i=1}^{i=N} L_i \right) / N \quad (3)$$

$$L_v = \left(\sum_{i=1}^{i=N} L_i^2 D_i^2 \right) / \left(\sum_{i=1}^{i=N} L_i D_i^2 \right) \quad (4)$$

$$s = \left(\sum_{i=1}^{i=N} L_i / D_i \right) / N \quad (5)$$

$$s_v = \left(\sum_{i=1}^{i=N} L_i^2 D_i \right) / \left(\sum_{i=1}^{i=N} L_i D_i^2 \right) \quad (6)$$

Compression testing was carried out on cylindrical specimens of length 15 mm and diameter 9 mm. The platens were lubricated with boron nitride. Although compression testing has the advantage that premature test termination by specimen tensile fracture and the systematic fibre reorientation which occurs during torsion testing are both avoided, care must be taken that a true homogeneous steady state is being set up. Good platen lubrication and detection of the formation of kink bands (in which an assembly of fibres become misorientated) are thus important. Most of the testing described here was carried out under strain rate control: it was found that the flow stress plateau usually stabilized before the onset of any microstructural inhomogeneities, which was often identifiable on the curve as a reduction in stress. From the experiments carried out so far, it seems that a unique steady-state can be set up in this material by imposing either strain rate or flow stress.

RESULTS

An indication of the degree of whisker alignment and aspect ratio values can be obtained from the deep-etched micrographs shown in Fig. 1, referring to the material produced with the two different extrusion conditions (denoted A and B). Although there is obvious alignment and the homogeneity is good, the presence of misaligned whiskers and of relatively gross particulate matter (partly SiC, but also Mg₂Si, CoSi, Fe₂Si, etc, originating from both as-received whiskers and binder reaction products⁽¹⁶⁾) may also be noted. The number and volume averaged length and aspect ratio values for the two materials are shown in Table I.

A typical stress-strain curve is shown in Fig. 2. The steady-state flow stress was taken from the initial load plateau and converted to a true stress. A limited degree of both barrelling and global specimen shear was in some cases detectable by this point, but these are expected to be of little significance in terms of the flow stress value. Kinking and shear band formation often occurred at higher strains and frequently resulted in a load reduction. The flow stress data are summarized in Tables II and III. From the repeat tests carried out, the reproducibility of these data was found to be good. The results are presented graphically in Figures 3 and 4, which show flow stress versus strain rate data at 25°C and 170°C (for material A) and flow stress versus 1/T data at a fixed strain rate of 10⁻³ s⁻¹ for both materials.

Fig.1 SEM micrographs of (a) material A and (b) material B, after deep etching to reveal the whiskers

Fig.2. A typical curve showing engineering stress versus engineering strain for a fixed true strain rate

Fig.3 Flow stress/strain rate data for material A

Material	L (μm)	L _v (μm)	s	s _v
A	5.75	8.25	12.4	11.8
B	2.88	4.90	5.03	5.37

Table I Average whisker length and aspect ratio values for the two materials used

Strain rate (s^{-1})	10^{-1}	10^{-2}	10^{-3}	10^{-4}	10^{-5}	10^{-6}
σ_0 at 300 K (MPa)	-	-	372	326	250	174
	-	-	383	328	238	-
σ_0 at 443 K (MPa)	170	134	92	81	64	-
	184	135	93	78	62	-

Table II Variation of flow stress with strain rate at two temperatures for material for material A

Temperature (K)	298	373	443	523
σ_0 for $s=12.4$ (MPa) (material A)	372 383	165 164	92 93	44 57
σ_0 for $s=5.0$ (MPa) (material B)	311 308	133 135	73 74	36 36

Table III Variation of flow stress with temperature at a strain rate of 10^{-3} s^{-1}

Fig.4 Flow stress/temperature data for material A and material B

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The generic equation (1) can be written

$$\ln \sigma_0 = \frac{1}{n} \ln \dot{\epsilon} - \frac{p}{n} \ln \delta + \frac{Q}{nRT} - \frac{1}{n} \ln A \quad (7)$$

It follows that a plot of $\ln \sigma_0$ against $\ln \dot{\epsilon}$ should give a linear plot with a gradient of $(1/n)$, provided the same deformation mechanism remains dominant over the strain rate regime. Furthermore, if this is also the case for two different temperatures, the plots should be parallel with a vertical displacement of $(Q/nR)(1/T_1 - 1/T_2)$. In the present case, these conditions seem to be approximately satisfied by the data in Fig. 3, suggesting that the same mechanism is dominant over the temperature range from 25°C ($0.3T_m$) to 170°C ($0.5T_m$). Measurement of the gradients suggests a value for n of about 8-9, and the mean vertical displacement leads to a value for Q of about 80-90 kJ mole⁻¹.

The data in Fig. 4 are consistent with this, in that both plots appear to be approximately linear over the above temperature range, with a gradient which, for the above value of n , also suggests a figure for Q of about 80-90 kJ mole⁻¹. However, at higher temperatures the data appear to indicate a curved plot suggesting that the appropriate activation energy is in transition towards a somewhat higher value in this regime ($0.5-0.7T_m$). Although it is clear that further data points are needed, a crude attempt to map a gradient onto the higher temperature data points suggests that a figure of about 130-140 kJ mole⁻¹ may be appropriate. Both activation energies seem to be equally applicable to the two materials, suggesting that a change in aspect ratio over the range concerned does not affect the mechanism. A further estimate can, in principle, be made from Fig. 4, in that the vertical displacement between data points for the two materials can, according to equation (7), be equated to $p(\ln \delta_B - \ln \delta_A)$. A problem then arises in deciding whether a diffusion distance can be inferred from microstructural observations. It is tempting to set δ equal to the fibre half-length, with $(L_v/2)$ apparently the most logical choice, but it should be recognized that this may be premature unless the mechanisms of deformation have been clearly established: relaxation modes such as interfacial sliding or cavitation⁽¹⁷⁾ may exhibit very different sensitivity to fibre length, and the fibre aspect ratio may be important in some cases. If δ is taken as $L_v/2$ then, using the data in Table I, an estimate for p can be made as about -0.5. This implies that the dependence on fibre length is clearly identifiable, but relatively weak. This result should be compared with previous observations^(1,4) that whisker-reinforced metals are much more creep-resistant than particle-reinforced material, typically by a factor of at least 10 in strain rate, apparently as a consequence of a three-fold or so increase in aspect ratio. However, it should be recognized that the present study is the first in which specimens having whiskers with quantifiably different lengths have been compared in this way. Particles are larger in diameter and are normally random in orientation; they are expected to be lower in both stiffness and strength than whiskers.

These experimental estimates of activation energies may be compared with published diffusivity data. Only Protosov et al.⁽¹¹⁾ give an activation energy for volume diffusion of Li in the Mg-Li bcc phase, reported as about 135-140 kJ mole⁻¹. A second publication⁽¹²⁾ reports a single diffusivity value at 420°C, which is somewhat higher than the corresponding figure according to Protosov et al., but it is noted that the specimen probably had a very fine grain size and high dislocation density, which may account for the discrepancy. A complication exists in that the relevant transport process is really one of vacancy movement. Because the vacancy flux is proportional to both vacancy diffusivity (with an exponential dependence on enthalpy of vacancy migration) and the vacancy concentration gradient associated with a gradient of hydrostatic stress (with an exponential dependence on enthalpy of vacancy formation), the overall activation energy will be the same as for matrix atom diffusion⁽¹⁸⁾. However, it is unclear what value is appropriate when solute is present with a mobility significantly different from that of the matrix. Perhaps the solute diffusivity value is appropriate if it is the higher of the two and the solute is present at a sufficiently high concentration. In this instance, the Li level is 30 atomic %, so that vacancies can presumably move freely via Li atom jumps only. Unfortunately, the activation energy of Mg in the bcc phase does not seem to have been published, but the results reported here do seem to be broadly consistent with an interfacial or core diffusion process for 0.3-0.5 T_m and volume diffusion at higher temperatures, with Li diffusion being dominant in both cases. Some of the possible deformation mechanisms are illustrated schematically in Fig. 5. (Climb of Orowan loops⁽¹⁹⁾ would take place in a similar manner to the core diffusion mechanism shown.) The observation of a relatively high stress exponent, n , strongly suggests that dislocation mechanisms were dominant in these experiments, rather than mass transport processes. A provisional conclusion would therefore be that mechanisms (a) or (b) are rate-determining in the lower temperature regime and mechanism (c) becomes more significant at somewhat higher temperatures.

It may be noted that anomalously high activation energies or stress exponents have not been detected in these experiments. This may be a consequence of the internal stresses in the matrix generated by thermal expansion mismatch having been largely relaxed prior to testing in this matrix. As a result of this, and because the experiments were carried out at relatively low temperatures, the significance of their variation over the temperature range examined may have been small, in accordance with the effect predicted by equation (2).

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Fig.5 Schematics of possible deformation mechanisms

REFERENCES

- (1) T.G. Nieh. 'Creep Rupture of Silicon Carbide Reinforced Aluminium.' Metall Trans. 15A, (1984), 139 - 146.
- (2) J.R. Pickens, T.J. Langan, R.O. England and M. Liebson. 'A Study of the Hotworking Behaviour of SiC - Al Alloy Composites and their Matrix Alloys by Hot Torsion Testing.' Metall. Trans. 18A, (1987), 303 - 312.
- (3) N. Hansen, D. Juul Jensen and Y.L. Liu. 'Microstructure and Creep Strength of an Aluminium Composite with Silicon Carbide Fibres.' in 'Mechanical and Physical Behaviour of Metallic and Ceramic Composites.' S.I. Andersen et.al. (eds.), p.365 - 372, Riso (1988).
- (4) P. Jarry, W. Loue and J. Bouvaist. 'Rheological Behaviour of SiC/Al Composites.' F.L. Matthews et.al. (eds.), p. 2.350 - 2.361. Elsevier, (1987).
- (5) M.Y. Wu and O.D. Sherby. 'Superplasticity in SiC Whisker Reinforced Aluminium Alloy.' Scripta Met. 18, (1984), 773 - 776.
- (6) S.M. Pickard and B. Derby. 'Thermal Cycle Creep of Al/SiC Particulate Composite.' in 'Mechanical and Physical Behaviour of Metallic and Ceramic Composites.' S.I. Andersen et al (eds.), p. 447 - 452, Riso (1988)
- (7) J.C. Leflour and R. Locicero 'Influence of Internal Stresses Induced by Thermal Cycling on the Plastic Deformation Resistance of an Al/SiC Composite Material', Scripta Met, 21(1987) p.1071-1076
- (8) G.S. Daehn and T. Oyama 'The Mechanism of Thermal Cycling Enhanced Deformation in Whisker Reinforced Composites.' Scripta Met. 22, (1988), 1097 - 1102.
- (9) M. McLean. 'Thermal Stress for Dislocation Creep.' Acta Met. 33, (1985), 545 - 556.
- (10) J.H. Jackson, P.D. Frost, A.C. Loonan, L.W. Eastwood and C.H. Lonig. 'Magnesium - Lithium Base Alloys - Preparation, Fabrication and General Characteristics.' Trans. TMS-AIME. 185, (1949), 149 - 168.
- (11) E.N. Protasov, A.A. Gnilomedov and A.L. L'vov. 'Electrochemical Behaviour of Lithium - Magnesium Alloys in LiCl-KCl, LiCl-KCl-CsCl and LiF-LiCl-KCl Melts.' Translated from Elektrokimaya 14, (1978), 1296 - 1300, in UDC.541.136, p 1127 - 1130 (1979).
- (12) Y. Iwodate, M. Lassouan, F. Lantenme and M. Chemla, 'Electrochemical Study of Mass Transfer in Li - Mg and Li - Mg - Al Alloys.' J. App. Electrochem. 17, (1987), 385 - 398.
- (13) J.F. Mason, C.M. Warwick, J.A. Charles and T.W. Clyne. 'Magnesium - Lithium Alloys in Metal Matrix Composites - A Preliminary Review.' accepted for publication in J. Mat. Sci. (1989).
- (14) T.W. Clyne and J.F. Mason. 'The Squeeze Infiltration Process for Fabrication of Metal Matrix Composites.' Metall. Trans. 18A, (1987), 1519 - 1530.
- (15) C.A. Stanford-Beale and T.W. Clyne, 'Extrusion and High Temperature Deformation of Fibre Reinforced Aluminium.' to be published in Comp. Sci. and Technol. special issue on metal matrix composites (1989).
- (16) J.F. Mason and T.W. Clyne, 'Microstructural Development and Mechanical Behaviour of SiC Whisker Reinforced Mg - Li Alloys.' to be published in the proceedings of ECCM 3, Bordeaux, March (1989).
- (17) S.R. Nutt and A. Needleman, 'Void Nucleation at fibre ends in Al/SiC composites.' Scripta Met. 21, (1987), 705 - 710.
- (18) C.A. Stanford-Beale and T.W. Clyne. 'Deformation of Fibrous Metal Matrix Composites at Temperatures Close to the Matrix Solidus.' in 'Mechanical and Physical Behaviour of Metallic and Ceramic Matrix Composites.' S.I. Andersen et.al. (eds.), 479 - 484.
- (19) T. Mura, in 'Micromechanisms of Defects in Solids.' p. 406 - 414, Martinus Nijhoff (1987)

2. Fiber and Fiber/Matrix Interface

